

Report from study of data compression assessment

Deliverable D2.7

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

An increase in processing power enabled to increase resolution and the number of ensemble members for both weather and climate simulations during the last decades. As a result, the amount of model input and output data that needs to be stored and processed increased significantly. However, supercomputing storage capacities did not grow at the same rate as processing power. Today, data storage and data processing generates significant cost for weather and climate modelling centres.

This deliverable suggests three new compression methods to reduce data volume for model output of ensemble simulations. If the new methods are used, the number of bits that is used to store individual variables can be reduced to reduce overall data volume while keeping the loss of information minimal. Two of the new methods rely on similarities between ensemble members in ensemble forecasts. If these methods are used, numerical precision will be high when ensemble spread is small and precision will decrease with increasing ensemble spread throughout the forecast. The methods are tested for model output of operational ensemble forecasts at ECMWF.

2. Conclusion & Results

In this deliverable, we suggest three new data compression methods to store model output of ensemble simulations. The data compression methods allow a reduction of the number of bits that is used to store each variable within model output data. This results in a reduction of up to one third of the overall data volume. Using the new methods, the loss of information is much smaller when the number of bits is reduced when compared to the loss of information for conventional data compression methods. However, savings that can be achieved will be different for different model fields.

The most successful methods that are presented in this deliverable are using similarities of ensemble members to reduce the number of bits per variable with minimal loss of information. These methods link numerical precision to ensemble spread to provide high precision for model variables that can be predicted with low uncertainty (small ensemble spread) and low precision for model variables that show large uncertainties (large ensemble spread). We therefore call these methods “predictive data compression methods”. The use of predictive data compression methods to reduce data volume appears to be very promising in the context of numerical weather predictions. Significant savings can be achieved if the new methods are used. However, potential savings are different for different model fields.

This deliverable is only a summary of the work. The new methods are presented in more detail in a paper that was submitted to the Monthly Weather Review (*Dueben et al. 2018*)

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	No
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community	No

on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	No

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	No
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	No
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

It is one aim of work package 2 of ESIWACE to study new approaches to optimise the management of data output without deteriorating the information contained. This deliverable will present three new methods to store ensemble model output. The methods will be applied to model output of the Integrated Forecast System (IFS) at ECMWF and results will be discussed in the context of data compression. However, a much more detailed description of the methods and results can be found in *Dueben et al. 2018*.

Motivation

Weather and climate simulations are very data intensive. The data handling system of ECMWF provides access to over 210 petabyte of primary data and ECMWF's data archive grows by about 233 terabyte per day (see <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/computing/our-facilities/data-handling-system>). The overall data volume at weather and climate centres is still growing and more research into data compression will be required to find sustainable solutions for data storage in the future. To reduce cost for the storage of model data, several degrees of freedom can be optimised including output frequency, spatial resolution, the selection of fields that are stored, compression techniques that are used, and numerical precision.

There are two ways to compress data: Lossless compression allows to reproduce the original field exactly with no error. Unfortunately, it is difficult to design efficient lossless compression techniques for output from weather and climate models (*Hübbe and Kunkel 2013*). Therefore, lossy compression techniques are typically used in weather and climate modelling. Lossy techniques do not allow to reproduce the original data, but more significant savings can be achieved. Weather and climate models are typically running with double precision floating point precision with 64 bits per variable and model output is typically stored with either single precision floating point numbers with 32 bits per variable or in fixed point representation with 16, 24 or 32 bits per variable.

In this deliverable, we suggest new methods to store model output from ensemble simulations. The methods are lossy and exploit similarities between ensemble members to reduce data volume. They establish a link between predictability and numerical precision and use high precision for predictable forecast situations and low precision for unpredictable forecast situations. Due to the link between precision and forecast uncertainty, we call the new methods “predictive data compression methods”. It is the hope that the new compression methods will allow a reduction of the number of bits that is used to store each model variable for ensemble simulations to reduce overall data volume with no loss of relevant information.

On average, model error will grow with time in weather forecasts and precision will therefore decrease when the predictive data compression methods are used. If model error is showing a reliable exponential error growth over time, as expected for chaotic systems (see *Lorenz 1963*), numerical precision can also be reduced with forecast lead time to adjust numerical precision to forecast uncertainty (see *Cooper et al. 2018*). However, while a mean reduction of precision in time will not take into account the predictability of a specific forecast situation, the predictive compression methods will use the ensemble spread to optimise local precision.

Three new compression methods for ensemble data

There are two standard data formats for model input and output of weather and climate models: NetCDF and GRIB. This deliverable will focus on the use of GRIB which is the standard data format at ECMWF (https://www.wmo.int/pages/prog/www/WMOCodes/Guides/GRIB/GRIB2_062006.pdf). Here, global meteorological data is stored in form of two-dimensional horizontal fields for each vertical level. The maximal and minimal value of each field is diagnosed per model level and stored as floating-point number. The interval between these values is then divided into 2^n numbers that are used to store the individual field values with “n” being the number of bits that is stored per variable. Model fields are typically stored with $n=16$ but the number of bits can easily be adjusted by the user for all model fields and vertical levels. The size of model output files scales roughly linear with the number of bits per value. At ECMWF, no additional data compression is used on top of the representation of numbers with 16 bits per variable in the GRIB fixed point format.

In this work, we suggest three new compression methods that can be used to increase the density of information for each bit that is stored. It is the aim to reduce the number of bits that is used per variable while keeping the overall information content the same. The three methods are described in the following.

Method 1: Remove coarse resolution field

This method assumes that large-scale gradients in output data can be removed to reduce the spread between the minimal and maximal values per model level. If this is possible, numerical precision will increase since precision scales with the inverse of the difference between the maximal and minimal value. For Method 1, the data is mapped onto a coarser grid. The coarse grid information is stored at high precision and the coarse field is subtracted from the originally data. For the resulting fields -- that are essentially local perturbations from the coarse field -- numerical precision can be reduced stronger. The data on the coarse grid can be added to the perturbation field to restore the original fields. The coarse model fields need to be stored as additional fields. In principle, Method 1 could also be applied with a hierarchy of coarse resolution grids to optimise savings.

Method 2: Remove ensemble mean

Method 2 assumes that the ensemble mean can be removed from ensemble output data to reduce the spread between the minimal and maximal values per model level to increase numerical precision. For Method 2 the ensemble mean is calculated. The mean is stored at high precision and subtracted from the

originally data. For the resulting fields -- that are essentially perturbations from the ensemble mean for each ensemble member -- numerical precision can be reduced stronger. The ensemble mean can be added to the perturbation fields to restore the original fields. The ensemble mean needs to be stored as an additional field, but this overhead will be small for large ensembles.

Method 3: Remove ensemble spread

Method 3 is very similar to Method 2. However, the perturbation fields are also normalised by the local ensemble spread for each variable. Therefore, all data points are stored with the maximal value within the ensemble to be equal to 1.0 and the minimal value equal to 0.0 for each variable. Local precision is maximised. The ensemble mean and the ensemble spread need to be stored as additional fields but this overhead will be small for large ensembles.

Savings and quality

Table 1 shows the storage volume if ensemble data is stored using different methods. For this purpose, ECMWF has been running a 50-member ensemble of IFS and has been using a O640 grid to represent the model fields (with 640 grid-points between the equator and the pole). The additional fields that are required for Method 1, 2 and 3 will increase data volume slightly when compared to the standard method with the same number of bits.

Storage method / Output type	Output in grid-point space	Output in spectral space
Standard GRIB with 16 bits per variable	1.83	0.431
Standard GRIB with 10 bits per variable	1.14	0.270
Method 1 using an O320 Gaussian grid as coarse grid	1.61	Not applicable
Method 2	1.18	0.279
Method 3	1.22	0.287

Table 1: Storage volume in gigabytes for different storage methods. The perturbation fields of Method 1,2 and 3 are stored with 10 bits per value.

Figure 1 and 2 show results when the fields of geopotential height at 500 hPa in spectral space and surface pressure in grid-point space are stored with the new methods. The figures show the error when the number of bits per variable is reduced that was calculated against the default data format or against the forecast analysis (both stored with a larger number of bits). The three storage methods that are suggested in this deliverable perform well in all tests. Each of the three methods reduces the error significantly in comparison to the default storage method at the same precision level. However, it is worth to mention that results will be different if different model fields are considered.

We also found that Method 3 provided much better results compared to the standard data format when the variability of fields was changing strongly within a single model level (not shown here, see *Dueben et al. 2018*). This can be expected since the local precision is normalised by the local variability of the field due to the division by the ensemble spread.

Figure 1: L1 norm of absolute errors for geopotential height at 500 hPa in [m²/s²]. Left: The error was calculated in comparison to the same data stored in the default GRIB data storage format at 16 bits precision. Precision was reduced to 10 bits for the perturbation fields of Method 2 and 3. Right: The error was calculated in comparison to model analysis. Precision was reduced to 6 bits for the perturbation fields of Method 2 and 3. The lines of the default method with 16 bits and Method 2 are hardly visible since they overlap with the results for Method 3. Results for Method 1 are not plotted since Method 1 can only be used for grid-point fields.

Figure 2: L1 norm of absolute errors for surface pressure in [hPa]. Left: The error was calculated in comparison to the same data stored in the default GRIB data storage format at 16 bits precision. Precision was reduced to 10 bits for the perturbation fields of Method 2 and 3. Right: The error was calculated in comparison to model analysis. Precision was reduced to 6 bits for the perturbation fields of Method 2 and 3.

5. References (Bibliography)

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6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?
Submitted	New methods for data storage of model output from ensemble simulations	P. D. Dueben, M. Leutbecher, P. Bauer	Monthly Weather Review	Yes
Submitted	It may be possible to half the amount of data output by weather forecast models by reducing numerical precision with lead time	F. Cooper, P. D. Dueben, C. Denis, P. Ashwin and A. Dawson	Monthly Weather Review	Yes

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

We have submitted a paper with a detailed description of the results of this work to a high-quality journal with high visibility by the targeted audience of weather and climate modellers. The paper will be published with open-access to the general public. We have also presented results at relevant conferences.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None.

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

It is very difficult to develop methods for data compression of weather and climate model output that do not reduce the “information content” of the data. The nature of the different fields in weather and climate models (such as surface pressure, geopotential height, specific humidity...) is very different. Some fields vary by orders of magnitude within a single vertical level. Some of the fields are dominated by large-scale gradients, other fields show features at very small spatial scale. This makes it very difficult to justify the use of standard lossy data compression techniques. Some methods work well for some of the fields while they will not generate significant savings or remove relevant information for other fields. In general, domain scientists are always afraid that relevant information is lost if lossy compression techniques are used (see for example *Baker et al. 2016*). It is therefore important to develop methods to reduce data volume that are transparent and easy to understand by domain scientists.

Furthermore, many of the standard lossy data compression techniques will show different savings if different fields are compressed and the resulting data volume may vary for different forecasts even for the same field. These fields would be very difficult to handle in operational weather forecasts that are bound to tight deadlines and require knowledge about the maximum file size to optimise the timing for data processing. In contrast to most standard compression techniques, the methods that are presented in this deliverable will show the same data volume for all fields and all lead times. Data volume after compression will only depend on the number of bits that is used to store each variable.

Compression techniques can, in principle, generate significant savings if they are applied cautiously in close collaboration with domain scientists. Savings can indeed be very significant (for example reduce data volume by a factor of two). However, the amount of post-processing that is required for model fields can be significant and can also generate significant challenges for data centres.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

None.

10. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo record / link to website	Estimated number of persons reached
Other (Poster)	Peter Dueben (ECMWF) Poster on “Reduced numerical precision in data storage for weather and climate simulations” at EGU 2017	23-28 April 2017, Vienna (AT)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU2017-4970.pdf	100
Training	Peter Dueben (ECMWF) Talk on “Reduced Precision Computing for Earth System Modelling” at the	13-17 March. 2017 and 16-20 April 2018, ECMWF,	Scientific Community (higher education,	https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/OPTR/NWP+Training+Mater	15+15

	Advanced numerical methods for earth system modelling training course at ECMWF in 2017 and 2018	Reading (UK)	Research)	ial+2017?preview=/72127032/76407295/peter_dueben.pdf	
Participation to a conference	Peter Dueben (ECMWF) Talk on “To reduce numerical precision to achieve higher accuracy in weather and climate modelling” at the SIAM Conference on Mathematical and Computational Issues in the Geosciences	11-14 September 2017, Erlangen (DE)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	N/A	100
Other	Peter Dueben (ECMWF) invited seminar talk on “To reduce numerical precision to achieve higher accuracy in weather and climate modelling” at Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	29 January 2018, Richland (USA)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	N/A	30
Participation to a conference	Peter Dueben (ECMWF) Talk on “To reduce numerical precision to achieve higher accuracy in weather and climate modelling” at the SIAM conference on Parallel Processing for Scientific Computing	7-10 February 2018, Tokyo (JP)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	N/A	100
Participation to a conference	Peter Dueben (ECMWF) Talk on “To link precision to predictability in weather forecasts” b at the ReCoVER/PEN/SECURE LWEC meeting	11-12 January 2018, Leeds (UK)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	N/A	40

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.